

EXA4MIND

D7.1

Impact Master Plan

AUSTRALO

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Abstract

This document outlines the planning of the dissemination, communication, exploitation and standardisation strategies for the EXA4MIND Horizon Europe project. This planning will be of relevance throughout the duration of the project and will be revisited periodically as it progresses.

Keywords

Impact, communication, dissemination, exploitation, community building, outreach, stakeholder management, commercialisation, business models, intellectual property, standardisation, open source.

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Dissemination Levels

PU	Public	Public, fully open, e.g., website
SEN	Sensitive	Confidential to EXA4MIND project and Commission Services

Deliverable Types

R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC	Websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER	Software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
C&D&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DBMS	Database Management System
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EDD	Extreme Data Database
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EXAKI	EXA4MIND Kickstarter Initiative
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
FF	Force Fields
HE	Horizon Europe
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPDA	High-Performance Data Analytics
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KEA	Key Exploitable Asset
MD	Molecular Dynamics
ML	Machine Learning
PPP	Public and Private Partnerships
PU	Public, fully open. e.g., website
R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RTOS	Research and Technology Organisations
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

Table of Partners

Short name	Partner
IT4I@VSB	IT4Innovations at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (IT4Innovations) https://www.it4i.cz/en
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities https://www.lrz.de/english/
METU	Middle East Technical University (METU) https://www.metu.edu.tr/
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab https://www.australo.org/
EURAXENT	Euraxent https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraxent/
CVUT	Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics at the Czech Technical University (CIIRC CTU) https://www.ciirc.cvut.cz/
VALEO	Valeo https://www.valeo.com/en/valeo-ai/
TERRAVIEW	Terraview https://www.terraview.co/
ALTRNATIV	Altrnativ https://altrnativ.com/

Executive Summary

This deliverable sets the framework, guidelines and means for EXA4MIND’s overarching communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The proposed document has also been conceived as the blueprint to design and build an ad hoc stakeholder collaboration framework to identify the ecosystem of entities impacted by the project’s innovations and expected outcomes. Moreover, these plans shall be supported by solid internal governance and continuous monitoring procedures to ensure that consortium members are always in the loop of ongoing outreach activities and share a common unified vision for the project.

The strategies set out in this document aim to:

- ◆ **Ensure the development** of appropriate means of communication of the project’s results outside of its consortium to raise awareness.
- ◆ **Increase the project’s impact** on the identified target audiences for further commercial and research purposes.
- ◆ **Foster stakeholders’ engagement** with the consortium to give consistency and continuity to the project’s findings and expected outcomes.

These plans will be subject to constant evaluation and revision throughout the EXA4MIND project, so as to have a constantly updated and accurate depiction of the progress made and challenges ahead. Within EXA4MIND’s official work plan, the present deliverable (**D7.1 – Impact Master Plan**) is presented as a fundamental part of **WP7 – Outreach, Exploitation and Collaboration**. It encompasses tasks **T7.1 – Stakeholder Collaboration Framework**, **T7.2 – Dissemination and Communication**, **T7.3 – Exploitation, Innovation Management & Sustainability** and **T7.4 – Standardisation & Open Source Plan**.

While all partners in the consortium are expected to actively contribute to EXA4MIND’s outreach activities in WP7, this work package –and D7.1 specifically– are led by AUSTRALO, who will apply their marketing expertise and proprietary methodologies to help partners unlock the full potential of their research and innovation. Other key actors in WP7 are EURAXENT, in charge of the creation of a long-term sustainability plan for the project, and BADW-LZR, who will lead the efforts on identifying potential contributions to standardisation and open source.

Following WP7’s **expected delivery plan**, milestone MS20 – EXA4MIND’s project website (**EXA4MIND 2023b**) was achieved back in month 2. Next in line are milestone MS21 – A first overview of the cooperation actions with sister projects funded under the same topic and other EU initiatives (**EXA4MIND 2023c**), and milestone MS23 – A first overview on publication efforts (**EXA4MIND 2023d**). Both are due month 12 and will be subsequently updated in month 24. Finally, milestone MS25 – EXA4MIND’s kickstarter launch (**EXA4MIND 2025c**), is expected to be achieved by month 30.

1 Introduction

The main goal of WP7 is to fast-track and amplify knowledge transfer between EXA4MIND and its target stakeholder base, reinforcing the value streams of the project and capitalising on the results obtained.

The **specific objectives** – as stated in the Description of Action (DoA)– that D7.1 intends to address at this early stage of the project are the following:

- ◆ Develop and operate a collaboration framework that will enable identifying and building synergies with a range of target groups and communities.
- ◆ Design and implement dissemination and communication strategies to efficiently raise awareness about the outcomes of the project, promoting the activities and results among a critical mass.
- ◆ Assess the footprint of the project through performance indicators while developing exploitation, sustainability and business models of the key results to be delivered.
- ◆ Develop an effective framework regarding Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management, technology transfer and fair law enforcement.
- ◆ Actively contribute to relevant standardisation bodies and committees.

As a general rule, all communication and dissemination activities for EXA4MIND will be designed with the core principles of **inclusiveness, equality** and **transparency** as main cornerstones. A well planned, engaging and agile communication and dissemination plan considers the impact of external factors and challenges in its execution and effectiveness while also unlocking the potential to maximise the project’s visibility and reach.

Although communication and dissemination are by two highly interlinked activities (see **Figure 1**), in this document they are addressed separately (see **Section 3** and **4**), though always in close dependence on one another. It is obvious that similarities and convergences exist and those will be carefully examined throughout the whole lifespan of the project.

Figure 1 EXA4MIND's Communication and Dissemination Flows

1.1 Purpose and Scope

D7.1 – Impact Master Plan presents EXA4MIND’s vision for communication, dissemination and exploitation in the early stage of the project. As such, it should be regarded as a living document and consequently, subject to changes during the three-year duration of the project. To fully reflect this ever-changing scenario, D7.1 is only the first in a series of WP7 deliverables and will be followed by:

- ◆ Two interim progress reports (due month 18): **D7.2 – Interim Dissemination and communication report (EXA4MIND 2024a)** and **D7.3 – Interim Market analysis and exploitation report (EXA4MIND 2024b)**.
- ◆ Two final progress reports (due month 36): **D7.4 – Final Dissemination and communication report (EXA4MIND 2025a)** and **D7.5 – Final Market analysis and exploitation report (EXA4MIND 2025a)**.

These batch reports will present the highlights and the full track-record of outreach efforts undertaken throughout the project – including quantifiable results and an assessment of the project’s activities impact on new business opportunities, knowledge creation and standardisation.

From an internal perspective, all expected work in WP7 has been carefully planned into two operational stages, which are fully detailed below.

1.1.1 First Stage – Setup and Preliminary Actions

This initial phase (see **Figure 2**) spans the time between the project’s official kick-off and the submission of **D7.2 (EXA4MIND 2024a)** and **D7.3 (EXA4MIND 2024b)** in month 18. It also coincides with the project’s first official review period and thus, the ambition throughout is double fold:

- ◆ First, to internally validate the relevant stakeholders who might have an interest in EXA4MIND’s Key Exploitable Assets (KEA) and clearly map the nature of their interest (commercial, research, etc.).
- ◆ Second, to craft a specific value proposition based on the project’s results for each stakeholder segment identified and assess the current status of the landing markets for EXA4MIND innovations.

This first stage will thus be concerned with setting the foundations for the project’s key impact pathways (see **Section 5** for more details), which are the following:

- ◆ **Project’s ecosystem:** a mapping of all the various segments and key actors with a potential interest in the Key Expect Assets (KEAs) of the project.
- ◆ **Market readiness:** an evaluation of market conditions, including Market Readiness Level (MRL), the competition landscape and potential sustainable business models for EXA4MIND.

- ◆ **Value proposition:** definition of a specific value proposition for those KEAs with significant commercial and/or research potential, in order to assess whether or not the different segments identified might have an interest in them, and to define the nature of such interest.

Figure 2 Timeline for EXA4MIND’s First Operational Stage

1.1.2 Second Stage – Reaching Maturity

The second and final stage (see **Figure 3**) is intended to build upon the outcomes from the first to exploit already validated knowledge and accelerate innovation and scaling-up efforts within the EXA4MIND’s ecosystem. In this sense, critical legal and commercial aspects related to the future exploitation of the project will be adequately addressed. All findings and recommendations derived from this exercise will be published within **D7.4 (EXA4MIND 2025a)** and **D7.5 (EXA4MIND 2025b)**.

These deliverables will include:

- ◆ A **business plan** based on a business model canvas for each specific KEA with commercial value, in order to ensure the continuity of EXA4MIND activities long-term and beyond the project’s official end date.
- ◆ An **IPR and knowledge management assessment**, to discuss all activities related to the use and exploitation of the project results and knowledge transfer mechanisms.

Figure 3 Timeline for EXA4MIND’s Second Operational Stage

1.2 Document Structure

The present document has been structured in the following way:

- ◆ **Section 1** is the Introduction, where the purpose and scope of the deliverable are first presented.
- ◆ **Section 2** focuses on the project’s engagement strategy, where the full ecosystem of organisations surrounding the project is presented and an ad hoc methodology for community building is proposed.
- ◆ **Section 3** and **4** outline EXA4MIND’s communication and dissemination plans, describing for both the main goals, timelines, tools and resources.
- ◆ **Section 5** and **6** introduce the project’s exploitation plan and its envisioned contributions to standardisation and open source. Here, foreseen KEAs are further discussed in the context of the wider exploitation strategies by individual partners and the consortium as a whole.
- ◆ **Section 7** lays out the internal governance and monitoring procedures necessary to align all communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts within the consortium.
- ◆ **Section 8** wraps up with the conclusions of this deliverable and shares final remarks and next steps.

2 Engagement Strategy

EXA4MIND will build an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework**, following AUSTRALO’s own proprietary methodology, explained below, to continuously develop and strengthen communication streams with key stakeholder groups, reinforcing the impact pathways of the projects through direct, meaningful interactions with its stakeholder base.

The project’s engagement strategy follows an iterative approach based on 6-month sprints along 3 phases (see **Figure 4**) to incrementally build and reinforce engagement.

Figure 4 EXA4MIND Stakeholder Collaboration Framework

2.1 Scout – Building a Stakeholder Map

As can be derived from **Table 1** below, EXA4MIND’s consortium comprises 9 leading organisations from technology and data provision, research and academia and the industrial realms: a powerful mix of universities, research centres, large companies, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and a natural person across Europe.

Sector	Partners
Research and Academia	IT4I@VSB, BADW-LRZ, METU, CVUT
Industry and SMEs	VALEO, AUSTRALO, TERRAVIEW, ALTRNATIV
Natural person	EURAXENT

Table 1 Overview of Sectors and Profiles Covered by EXA4MIND’s Consortium Members

The project will leverage the consortium’s leadership and participation in active ecosystems to create synergies, bridging the collaboration between multidisciplinary profiles in EXA4MIND’s ecosystem. Their already consolidated networks will be the ideal starting point to engage with other organisations in the project’s main focus areas: responsible development and exploitation of Extreme Data, automated data management, data analytics, supercomputing, Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The key outcome of this exercise is the so-called EXA4MIND’s **stakeholders map** (see **Figure 5**), a visual mind map that:

- ◆ Establishes a high-level baseline of relevant profiles/expertise for the project to liaise with.
- ◆ Identifies and displays links between key actors within the project’s ecosystem.
- ◆ Classifies and segments these audiences in terms of their perceived impact and influence on the project’s execution and success.
- ◆ Defines a common terminology to be referenced in all project’s documentation.

Figure 5 EXA4MIND's Key Target Groups

2.1.1 Key Target Groups

Building upon EXA4MIND’s high-level objectives and findings from previous iterations, the scouting phase first explores, maps and classifies the project’s target audience in terms of their relevance to the scope and impact of EXA4MIND’s work plan.

Technology and Data Providers

Key players working on research, innovation, business development and interoperability efforts around HPC and Extreme Data mining technologies. EXA4MIND will engage with key representatives to exchange and enforce the technology transfer of the outcomes, bridging the Open Innovation divide. This category includes research-oriented institutions (technical universities, research centres, spin-offs) and business-driven organisations (from highly risk-taking start-ups to innovation units in large-scale industry) that will contribute to the technical ambition of the project.

Industrial Ecosystem

Decision makers, managers and researchers from the industrial ecosystem who design and implement Extreme Data mining solutions and analytics targeting EXA4MIND's application case focus areas: the automotive sector, molecular dynamics, health and agriculture. The project will engage with this ecosystem to obtain hands-on requirements and feedback that will support the implementation of the project and its application cases, understand internal processes, system integration and risk management, access quality data acquisition, raise wide-range awareness and trust on the positive impact High Performance Computing (HPC) and Extreme Data mining technologies will have in complex real-world scenarios.

Social Innovation Sector

The implementation of disruptive data mining and analytics in an industrial environment is not just a mere technical question. Human and ethical factors are compulsory to facilitate a transformation compliant with the workforce's needs. Social science needs to be involved to understand how people interact with these solutions, making their design more natural for the user and relevant to the sector.

Partnerships, Networks and Working Groups

EXA4MIND builds upon the experience and active involvement of consortium members in related initiatives and projects (e.g., **LEXIS**,¹ **EuroCC**,² **IO-SEA**,³ **PRACE**,⁴ **GeRDI**,⁵ **COREnect**,⁶ **AI-PRISM**,⁷ **ELISE/ELLIS**⁸ and **SESAME**⁹. It also takes advantage of new

¹ Lexis project website. <https://lexis-project.eu/web/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

² EuroCC website. https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/research-innovation-0/our-projects/eurocc_en (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³ IO-SEA project website. <https://iosea-project.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁴ PRACE website. <https://prace-ri.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁵ GeRDI Project website. <https://www.gerdi-project.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁶ COREnect website. <https://www.corenect.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁷ AI-PRISM project website. <https://aiprism.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁸ ELISE project profile. ELLIS website. <https://ellis.eu/elise> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁹ SESAME project CORDIS profile. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/821875> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

leads generated by second-degree partnerships and new opportunities as an outcome of the interacting phase, including emerging Public and Private Partnerships (PPP) and other related Horizon Europe projects.

Focus areas of special relevance for EXA4MIND are computer and data science, Big Data, HPC, AI and open science and research. They are presented and further outlined in the following sections, along with other synergistic initiatives currently operating in the European playground.

Computer Science, Data Science and Big Data

Examples of initiatives in the spheres of computer science, data science and Big Data identified by the consortium are: **DAIRO/BDVA**¹⁰, **NFDI – The German National Research Data Infrastructure**¹¹, **GCS – Gauss Centre for Supercomputing**¹², **ELLIS – the European Laboratory of Learning and Intelligent Systems**¹³, and **ADRA – the recently created European Partnership on Artificial Intelligence, Data and Robotics**¹⁴.

Additionally, here is also a non-comprehensive list of EU initiatives and European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) working in the realms of Big Data, HPC, AI or cross-border data sharing infrastructures that might be of interest to EXA4MIND for networking purposes:

- ◆ **DIHNET**¹⁵: a project to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, focusing on regional DIHs.
- ◆ **DAMAS**¹⁶: focused on two key digital technologies indicated by the Digital Europe Programme (DEP): HPC and AI. It specialised on key digital enablers: cloud and edge computing; Big Data analytics, high performance data analytics; computational fluid dynamics; virtual reality/augmented reality; fast prototyping including 3D printing; additive manufacturing; digital twin simulation and modelling; space technologies – geo information and sustainable computing.
- ◆ **ATTRACT**¹⁷: defines an ambitious plan to support SMEs and public entities in their digital transformation and consolidation through the full exploitation of the synergetic potential between AI and HPC.

¹⁰ BDVA website. <https://www.bdva.eu/DAIRO> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹¹ NFDI website. <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹² Gauss Centre website. <https://www.gauss-centre.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹³ ELLIS Society website. <https://ellis.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹⁴ Adra website. <https://adr-association.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹⁵ DIHNet website. <https://dihnet.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹⁶ DAMAS profile at the European Digital Innovation Hubs Network. <https://european-digital-innovation-hubs.ec.europa.eu/edih-catalogue/damas> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹⁷ ATTRACT profile at the European Digital Innovation Hubs Network. <https://european-digital-innovation-hubs.ec.europa.eu/edih-catalogue/attract> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

- ◆ **EUHubs4Data**¹⁸: the European federation of Data Driven Innovation Hubs for data-driven innovation and experimentation.
- ◆ **DIH-World**¹⁹: an initiative to accelerate the uptake of advanced digital technologies by European manufacturing SMEs by supporting them in building sustainable competitive advantages and reaching global markets.

High Performance Computing and Artificial Intelligence

A preliminary list of AI and HPC initiatives that EXA4MIND has identified as relevant are listed below:

- ◆ **The European AI Alliance**²⁰: a multi-stakeholder forum engaged in a broad and open discussion of all aspects of AI development and its impact on the economy and society. Additionally, the AI Alliance community continues to promote trustworthy AI by sharing best practices²¹ among the members and by helping developers of AI and other stakeholders to apply key requirements through the ALTAI tool²², a practical Assessment List for Trustworthy AI.
- ◆ **AI on Demand**²³: the first European AI on-demand platform and ecosystem.
- ◆ **EuroHPC JU**²⁴: a joint undertaking between the EU, European countries and private partners to develop a world-class supercomputing ecosystem in Europe.
- ◆ **ETP4HPC**²⁵: an industry-led think-tank promoting European HPC research and innovation to support Europe's competitiveness.

Application Case Links

EXA4MIND proposes 4 application cases fully aligned to the vision of the common European Data Spaces and covering most of its focus areas (e.g., Industry, Health and Agriculture).

Open Science and Research

Open science refers to a specific approach to scientific research that prioritises transparency, nurtures collaboration, and fosters accessibility to ensure results, data, and methods are publicly available to the global community.

¹⁸ EUHubs4Data website. <https://euhubs4data.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

¹⁹ DIH-World website. <https://dihworld.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²⁰ European AI Alliance website. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-ai-alliance> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²¹ European AI Alliance: best practices. <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/best-practices> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²² ALTAI tool website. <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²³ <https://www.ai4europe.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²⁴ EuroHPC website. https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²⁵ ETP4HPC website. <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

Relevant Initiatives

EXA4MIND benefits from the very active participation of its partners in very diverse working groups and initiatives around HPC and Extreme Data mining and analytics. These initiatives bring together community efforts to drive common discussions and strategies. The project members have ties to a number of ongoing initiatives (see **Table 2**) and will thus try to capitalise on the already consolidated status of this kind of initiatives.

Segment	Initiative	EXA4MIND's liaison
Data science & Big Data	<u>The Alliance for Digital Trust</u>	ALTRNATIV
Data science & Big Data	<u>ACM - Association for Computing Machinery</u>	METU
Data science & Big Data	<u>EUDAT – Collaborative Data Infrastructure</u>	IT4I@VSB
Data science & Big Data	<u>EOSC - European Open Science Cloud</u>	IT4I@VSB
Data science & Big Data	<u>BDVA – Big Data Value Association</u>	IT4I@VSB, AUSTRALO
Data science & Big Data	<u>NFDI – The German National Research Data Infrastructure</u>	BADW-LRZ
Data science & Big Data	<u>iRODS</u>	IT4I@VSB
Computer science	<u>IEEE – Computer Society</u>	METU, IT4I@VSB
Open Science & Research	<u>RDA (Research Data Alliance) and interest group RDARI</u>	BADW-LRZ
Open Science & Research	<u>RDA-DE</u>	BADW-LRZ
HPC	<u>ETP4HPC – European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing</u>	IT4I@VSB
HPC	<u>EuroHPC JU</u>	IT4I@VSB
HPC	<u>EuroCC</u>	IT4I@VSB, BADW-LRZ, METU
HPC	<u>GCS – Gauss Centre for Supercomputing</u>	BADW-LRZ
Agriculture	<u>Swiss Food and Nutrition Valley Association</u>	TERRAVIEW
Agriculture	<u>Agropole</u>	TERRAVIEW
6G	<u>6GSNS JU Associate membership</u>	TERRAVIEW
AI	<u>prg.ai Association</u>	VALEO, CVUT

Automotive	Automotive Industry Association	VALEO
AI	European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems (ELLIS)	CVUT
AI	Computer vision foundation (CVF)	CVUT

Table 2 EXA4MIND's links to open science

Related EU Projects

There are several other funded projects in the intersection of Extreme Data, automated data management, data analytics, supercomputers, ML and AI, with whom EXA4MIND will aim to connect with the ambition to align synergies and take those aspects further.

Primarily, EXA4MIND is expected to collaborate closely with Horizon Europe (HE) funded projects under topic **HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05: Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions**²⁶. Other projects selected within this call are:

- ◆ **EXTRACT**²⁷: a European project that works to provide a distributed data-mining software platform for extreme data across the compute continuum.
- ◆ **NEARDATA**²⁸: an initiative to create an extreme data infrastructure mediating data flows between object storage and data analytics platforms across the compute continuum.
- ◆ **EMERALDS**²⁹: a project developing mobility analytics as a service (MAaaS) toolset which will set itself to processing the data on the same devices that collect the data or nearby devices to improve response times and privacy of sensitive data.
- ◆ **EFRA**³⁰: an initiative that works on extreme food risk analytics.
- ◆ **SYCLOPS**³¹: a project aiming to democratise hardware acceleration for AI with RISC-V and SYCL.
- ◆ **Graph-Massivizer**³²: a project researching and developing a high-performance, scalable, and sustainable platform for information processing and reasoning based on the massive graph representation of extreme data.

Additionally, there are two initiatives, that already came to an end, with which EXA4MIND has identified strong synergies with and will leverage on:

²⁶ EU funding & tender opportunities website. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl4-2022-data-01-05> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

²⁷ EXTRACT project website. <https://extract-project.eu/extract-project-kicks-off/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²⁸ NEARDATA project website. <https://neardata.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

²⁹ EMERALDS project website. <https://emeralds-horizon.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³⁰ CORDIS EFRA profile. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093026> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³¹ CORDIS SYCLOPS profile. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092877> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³² Graph-Massivizer project website. <https://graph-massivizer.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

- ◆ **LEXIS**³³: (finished in December 2021) this project built an advanced workflow and data-flow orchestration platform, leveraging EUDAT. The LEXIS approaches to distributed infrastructure, leveraging EUDAT and providing staging, data-ingest and orchestrator Application Programming Interfaces (API) will serve as a blueprint for EXA4MIND DBMS – centric approaches. EXA4MIND will leverage on the LEXIS project results.
- ◆ **DICE**³⁴: this project provided cutting-edge data management services and a significant amount of storage resources for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This project warrants that EXA4MIND is on a successful path using EUDAT tools in order to connect to the EOSC and European Data Spaces.

Other Horizon Europe (HE) themes connected to EXA4MIND are information and communication technologies, food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment.

Policy Makers

EXA4MIND will contribute to policy task forces or working groups (where and when relevant), shaping policies related to data use and digital transformation. The primary representative of this category will be the European Commission, including contributions to the following overarching policy landscapes:

European Clusters and the EU Industrial Strategy

In 2022, 30 Euroclusters were launched to implement the EU Industrial Strategy. Euroclusters are cross-sectoral, interdisciplinary and trans-European strategic initiatives of industry clusters and other economic actors, such as research organisations and companies.

European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud

The European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud³⁵ aims to foster the development and deployment of next generation edge and cloud technologies and reinforce the position of European industry on these key areas by catering to the needs of businesses and public administrations processing sensitive data in the industrial data realm.

³³ LEXIS Project website. <https://lexis-project.eu/web/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³⁴ DICE project website. <https://www.dice-eosc.eu/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³⁵ European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud website. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-alliance> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

The European Data Strategy and European Common Data Spaces

The European data strategy³⁶ aims to make the EU a leader in a data-driven society through the creation of a so-called ‘The digital single market’ where data can freely flow in compliance with current privacy and data protection and observing fair rules for both data access and use. In this line, Common European data spaces will ensure data availability while keeping data generators always in control of their data.

Society at Large

EXA4MIND will encourage a common understanding and trust of the positive impact of supercomputing applications for Europe’s industrial ecosystem, raising awareness of the mindset shift linked to the transition from technology-driven progress to a thoroughly human-centric and sustainable approach towards data mining. Accessible content will be produced to engage with society as a whole and reinforce EXA4MIND’s position in the public sphere.

2.2 Interact –Breaking the Ice

This is the phase where EXA4MIND will seek to directly collaborate with advocate initiatives. Whenever relevant, the project will formally join specific task forces and working groups, contribute to scientific publications and participate in events. Feedback extracted from previous sprints will be used to improve the efficiency and impact of these interactions.

EXA4MIND’s Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework is designed to continuously develop, strengthen and revisit communication streams with key stakeholder groups. This methodology relies on a constant, carefully designed throughput of promotional activities and campaigns, conceived to incite and maintain the interest of our audience throughout the project’s lifecycle, as per the core values of the Agile Manifesto³⁷: putting individuals and interactions over processes and tools, prioritising results over comprehensive documentation, nurturing collaboration over formality, and focusing on responding to change over following a rigid plan.

From the initial visualisation of EXA4MIND’s stakeholder map shown in **Section 2.1**, stakeholders have been further categorised in terms of their influence and interest. **Figure 6** illustrates the results of this step.

³⁶ European Strategy for Data website. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

³⁷ Manifesto for Agile Software Development: <http://agilemanifesto.org/> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

Figure 6 EXA4MIND's Stakeholders Depicted in Terms of their Interest and Influence

2.3 Learn – Maintaining Interest

In this last phase, the consortium will learn and adapt based on how these interactions play out and insights obtained from stakeholder consultation (i.e., quick surveys or interviews to gather valuable external feedback about the project and its operation, see **Section 4.2** for more details). These best practices will in turn feed the next scouting sprint.

These efforts will in turn inform a more exhaustive contextualization of EXA4MIND's stakeholder ecosystem. Thus, we arrive at **Figure 7**, where engagement levels are charted for each of the project's key audiences. This classification considers the following tiers:

- ◆ **Core team:** is part of the project itself, takes part in all ongoing communication and exchanges.
- ◆ **Involved:** regularly provides input or helps the project move work forward, though EXA4MIND is not their sole focus.
- ◆ **Informed:** wants to stay up to date and will provide feedback/input when prompted.

Figure 7 EXA4MIND's Stakeholder Mapping by their Engagement Level

3 Communication Plan

EXA4MIND’s communication plan takes full advantage of the versatility and multidisciplinary permeating the project’s ecosystem needs for communication to primarily focus on generating awareness by conveying key aspects and benefits of the project to all target audiences and end users. Although communication objectives may be treated as a single entity, some relate to specific target groups only and thus, will be approached through specific tools and activities as the project evolves.

EXA4MIND **overall objectives for communication** adhere to the following directives:

- ♦ **Plan:** craft and deliver top-level messages about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- ♦ **Reach:** communicate technical and scientific results and benefits to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- ♦ **Act:** build a solid community/ecosystem.
- ♦ **Convert:** identify leads within the project’s ecosystem and explore their unmet needs and interests to build a solid customer base/ecosystem for future dissemination and exploitation of results.
- ♦ **Engage:** raise awareness among specialised and non-specialised audiences of the added value of EXA4MIND to reach the widest possible community.

By addressing these objectives in a targeted and strategic manner, the communication plan will help ensure that EXA4MIND’s mission, activity and results are effectively communicated and understood, leading to broader engagement and support for the project goals.

To further cement this philosophy, all multimedia materials produced in the context of the project will follow EXA4MIND’s visual guidelines to cultivate branding recognition and strive to be memorable and easily understandable. This will help EXA4MIND concepts and benefits to become instantly identifiable to a wider audience while growing and maintaining further interest towards the project and its key outcomes. Similarly, relevant information will be extracted from project deliverables; interviews with partners, pilot case studies; industry reports; and will be relayed through EXA4MIND communication channels to further support active user engagement.

EXA4MIND’s communication related KPIs are presented in **Table 3**, alongside their expected targets.

Focus	KPIs	Target
Community	Contact points	5,000
	EU associations and create synergies with EDIHs	10+
Online channels	Unique average monthly website visitors	300
	Social media monthly impressions	4,500
	Social media followers	2,500
	Newsletter	4/year
	Features in external newsletters	4
Promotional materials	Hard copy items	1,000
	Graphic elements (e.g., infographics, banners)	100+
	Videos (teasers and interviews)	3

Table 3 EXA4MIND’s Communication KPIs

3.1 Phases and Timeline for Communication

Communication activities will be implemented in 3 different phases, as can be seen in **Figure 8**. The ultimate goal is to iteratively build an engaged community of developers and end users who are willing to share an open, dedicated space for active interaction, collaboration and feedback.

Figure 8 Phases of EXA4MIND’s Communication Plan

3.1.1 Plan and Revisit (Month 1 – Month 6)

This initial planning phase focuses primarily on establishing key communication tools and channels, planning monitoring strategies and identifying potential target groups and stakeholders. The project’s visual identity (see **Section 3.2.1** for more details) and communication toolkit have already been established, and “icebreakers” (e.g., the project’s first press release, the official website launch) take the spotlight in this early stage.

3.1.2 Early Bird Communication (Month 7 – Month 12)

During this second phase, early bird activities will take place to communicate to a wider public and to specific communities about the existence of the project and its forthcoming activities and actions. Emphasis is given to online tools (e.g., social media, awareness publications and newsletters) as they tend to have wider reach.

3.1.3 Targeted Communication (Month 13 – Month 36)

The focus will shift towards targeted communication activities for this final phase, such as long-form articles highlighting specific project outcomes or results, or in-depth features on the evolution of EXA4MIND’s application cases, hosting and/or participating in relevant events (physical or online), and producing targeted communication material (i.e., videos, infographics, factsheets) for specific members of the identified community.

3.2 Communication Toolkit and Resources

A series of communication tools have already been made available to allow the project to reach the right audiences in a cohesive and effective way. This toolkit will be tailored to the specific communication needs for all phases defined above.

The preliminary list of channels and platforms it covers is presented here and further explained in the following sections:

- ◆ **EXA4MIND’s visual identity:** including all logo declinations and applications, official fonts and colour palettes.
- ◆ **Online channels** (see **Figure 9**): the project’s official website, social media accounts and newsletter platform of choice.
- ◆ **Promotional material:** the first batch of promotional materials, including EXA4MIND’s flyer, poster, roll-up banner and merchandise.

Figure 9 EXA4MIND's Communication Toolkit – Online Channels

3.2.1 Branding and Identity System

EXA4MIND's complete visual identity was designed and officially adopted during the first month of the project. The branding and identity system includes the project's visual guidelines and branding assets and identity system.

The rationale behind the chosen logo design revolves around two key elements:

- ◆ A **diamond shape** to symbolize the three abstract concepts that are core to EXA4MIND: value, mining and complexity.
- ◆ The **paths and interconnections** of data, finally coming together to form the initial "e" in EXA4MIND.

Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 12 below serve to showcase EXA4MIND's main logo and icon, its declinations (i.e., vertical/horizontal and positive/negative variations) and some example applications. Figure 13 displays the official typography (Work Sans for standard texts, Work Sans Semibold for headings and titles) and colour codes.

Figure 10 EXA4MIND's Main Logo Declinations

Figure 11 EXA4MIND’s Icon Variations

Figure 12 EXA4MIND’s Examples of Logo Applications

typography

Titles

Work Sans
Semibold

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Longer texts

Work Sans

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download the font family [here](#)

color guide

primary

#031B69

#FF3299

secondary

#8ACDEA

#6096BA

#FFE631

#BC5FF9

neutrals

#FFFFFF

#5E747C

Figure 13 EXA4MIND's Typography and Colour Codes

3.2.2 Online Channels

Project Website

EXA4MIND's public website (**Figure 15**) is a key instrument to boost the visibility of the project and the main entry point to showcase its vision and approach, news, findings and results, introducing visitors to the project's rationale and educating them on its fundamental concepts.

A complete sitemap is presented below in **Figure 14**. The website structure and navigation menus will be expanded and fine-tuned as the project progresses and there is more content hosted online.

Project website <https://exa4mind.eu>

Figure 14 EXA4MIND's Website Map

Figure 15 EXA4MIND’s Website – Home Page

Helpdesk and Contact Point

EXA4MIND has set up a corporate contact point for all stakeholders with a 72-hours reply commitment to manage general enquiries, collaboration requests, bug-tracking and feature requests. This channel will be complemented with a FAQ section to be embedded on the website.

Contact point	info@exa4mind.eu
----------------------	--

Social Media

Social media offers a swift, cost-effective medium for reaching interest groups and communities. EXA4MIND has established and currently maintains an active presence on both Twitter (**Figure 16**) and LinkedIn (**Figure 17**), as they have proven to be highly effective in engaging with technology-driven communities. A dedicated YouTube channel will also be set up to upload and share EXA4MIND’s videos (e.g., workshop recordings, official presentation videos and/or any other multimedia content produced throughout the project’s run).

EXA4MIND’s overall strategy for social media stems from the following set of key rules for online engagement:

- ◆ **Post regularly:** effective posting on social media relies on consistency. EXA4MIND will employ optimization and scheduling tools (e.g., **Hootsuite**³⁸) to post regularly and at optimal times in the day – when most traffic on Twitter and LinkedIn occurs for our target audience –, thus enhancing engagement and organic views.
- ◆ **Use references and keywords:** linking posts to key players by actively tagging relevant accounts in the conversation and including trending hashtags – especially from our partners – to try and leverage on their existing networks, thus amplifying the project’s voice. This helps provide a wider outreach, leveraging the existing audience from their accounts.
- ◆ **Actively share content from the community:** sharing news and information not just related to our project but also relevant to our community (e.g., news pieces of scientific, academic or industrial nature from news outlets across Europe) attracts more followers and helps gains more traction.
- ◆ **Tailor content to Twitter and LinkedIn:** there are inherent differences in tone between social media (e.g., LinkedIn vs. Twitter). A first approach might consider capitalizing on LinkedIn’s professional nature and more “serious” tone, and the general perception that information there tends to be more reliable. This means that individuals with genuine interest in the topics that EXA4MIND deals with will eventually invest more time reading what is shared on this platform. For this reason,

³⁸ Hootsuite website. <https://www.hootsuite.com> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

the information shared on LinkedIn needs to be carefully fine-tuned, through longer text, more detailed information and highly specific hashtags. Twitter posts are snippets of these, even though they bring across the same message.

- ◆ **Boost promotion of project content:** creating and promoting a variety of project content in our social media strategy is key for raising awareness about EXA4MIND across channels. For this reason, project articles will be often linked to via the project’s social media channels, often accompanied by appealing and easily recognisable visuals in the form of custom graphics and calls-to-action.

Figure 16 EXA4MIND’s Twitter Profile

Figure 17 EXA4MIND's LinkedIn Company Profile

Newsletters

The first issue of EXA4MIND's newsletter is already out (see **Figure 18**) and quarterly instalments will follow in due time. The project's newsletter will be published on both LinkedIn and **Brevo**³⁹, a GDPR-compliant Customer Relationship Management (CRM) suite for mailing campaign and lead generation. Brevo drives traffic and leads to EXA4MIND's website, while LinkedIn embedded newsletter functionalities will leverage the following benefits:

- ◆ Reaching a professional and targeted audience, making it an ideal medium to engage with stakeholders in technology applications.
- ◆ Expanding our network and capitalising on our existing connections to reach their extended networks, increasing the visibility of EXA4MIND's content.
- ◆ Encouraging engagement through likes, comments and shares, fostering interaction and discussion among our target audiences.
- ◆ Tracking performance with built-in analytics to monitor and refine strategies based on the insights gained from user engagement.

³⁹ Brevo website. <https://www.brevo.com> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

Figure 18 EXA4MIND's Newsletter - June 2023 Issue

3.2.3 Promotional Materials

Slide Decks and Infographics

Well-designed slide decks and infographics (**Figure 19**) are powerful engagement tools to share the project's vision and scope with specialised audiences in a clear, straightforward and visually attractive way.

Figure 19 EXA4MIND's First Set of Infographics

Printed Materials and Merchandising

The first batch of promotional materials is already available for EXA4MIND. It includes the project’s official flyer (Figure 20), poster and roll-up banner designs (Figure 21) in digital format to be printed when required (e.g., for display in events, workshops or fairs), together with branded merchandise that drives home EXA4MIND’s ideas via a more creative and sustainable medium.

Figure 20 EXA4MIND’s Promotional Materials – A5 Flyer, Coasters and Stickers

Figure 21 EXA4MIND’s Promotional Materials – Raffle Poster and Roll-up Banner

4 Dissemination Plan

EXA4MIND has developed a flexible dissemination plan that intends to raise awareness of project results, promoting understanding and encouraging action among key target audiences. The execution of this plan will facilitate the uptake of outcomes and best practices, as well as promote research insights and breakthroughs, thus reinforcing the impacts described in the DoA.

EXA4MIND’s dissemination areas, KPIs and targets are presented below in **Table 4**.

Area	KPIs	Target
Documentation	Project deliverables	31
Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific items in journals	10
	Peer-reviewed papers in conferences/workshops (including peer-reviewed posters)	15
	Awareness publications (including press releases)	50+
	Open Access downloads (Zenodo)	1,000+
Events	Featured events	30
	Webinars and workshops	12
	Unique participants	300

Table 4 EXA4MIND – Dissemination KPIs and Targets

4.1 Phases and Timeline for Dissemination

EXA4MIND’s dissemination plan will be implemented in 3 different phases, as presented in **Figure 22**. Though they can of course be extended or adjusted if necessary, these phases do not span the whole project timeline, but instead have clear start and end dates.

Figure 22 Phases of EXA4MIND's Dissemination Plan

4.1.1 Identify and Study (Month 1 – Month 6)

In this early phase, efforts will go towards analysing the project's stakeholder framework and its preliminary segmentation by profile and relevance. Special attention will be given to internal and external barriers that might slow down dissemination activities.

4.1.2 Outreach and Influence (Month 7 – Month 18)

During this second phase, the main goal will be to showcase EXA4MIND's first tangible achievements. All channels will be adequately tailored to find the proper means to engage and collaborate with identified target groups. Participation and/or hosting workshops, ad hoc events, tutorials/webinars (if necessary) will be a priority to help boost visibility.

4.1.3 Embrace and Accept (Month 19 – Month 36)

By the time the project reaches its final stretch, it is expected to attract more potential developers and end users interested in near-final results. All outcomes of the two earlier phases will be evaluated and, if necessary, priorities, measures and

dissemination channels will be refined. Further participation in events, workshops, conferences, together with partner contributions to publications in targeted specific media online, printed media and research journals will be key to broadcast the project's final insights and foster long-term sustainability of its results.

4.2 Dissemination Toolkit and Resources

As already mentioned in **Section 1**, communication and dissemination activities are inherently interlinked and therefore some tools are shared between both. **Figure 23** below displays some of the specific dissemination tools envisioned for EXA4MIND, which will be further expanded upon in the following sections.

Figure 23 EXA4MIND's Dissemination Toolkit

4.2.1 Online Channels

Open Science

Open science is a policy priority for the European Commission and the standard provision under which its research and innovation funding programmes operate. In order to comply with these set requirements, EXA4MIND will make use of available platforms at European level, such as:

- ◆ **European Open Science Cloud**⁴⁰: the EOSC Portal provides access to the European hub of research data, tools and services for innovation and education.
- ◆ **Open Research Europe**⁴¹: a fast publication and open peer review platform for research stemming from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and Euratom funding across all subject areas.

There is a dedicated **EXA4MIND Zenodo community** and repository already in place for the project (see **Figure 24**). Whenever conditions allow, as per our Data Management Plan (DMP) (**EXA4MIND 2023a**) and in line with the European Commission guidelines

⁴⁰ EOSC portal. <https://eosc-portal.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

⁴¹ Open Research Europe website. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu> (Accessed 23 June 2023)

for Open Science, documentation in the form of public deliverables will be made available through this repository.

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/exa4mind-heurope>

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the EXA4MIND project. The main content area lists four recent uploads, each with a search bar, version information, and a 'View' button. The uploads are:

- EXA4MIND Leaflet** (May 11, 2023 v01): EXA4MIND Consortium; EXA4MIND A5 dyptic. Uploaded on May 11, 2023.
- EXA4MIND Main Logo** (February 8, 2023 v1): AUSTRALO; EXA4MIND Main Logo. Uploaded on February 8, 2023.
- IT4I/EXA4MIND Joint Press Release** (January 30, 2023 v2): AUSTRALO; IT4I/EXA4MIND Press Release in Czech. Uploaded on January 31, 2023. 1 more version(s) exist for this record.
- EXA4MIND First joint press release** (January 16, 2023 v1): AUSTRALO; EXA4MIND project first joint press release. Project funded by Horizon Europe. Uploaded on January 16, 2023.

The right sidebar contains the following information:

- Community:** EXA4MIND (with logo)
- EXA4MIND project:** EXA4MIND, a brand new EU-funded project under the Horizon Europe programme, will build an Extreme Data platform that brings together Supercomputing and Big Data infrastructure, and will automate top-notch data analysis, data management and data staging. Ambitious applications in molecular dynamics, autonomous driving, smart agriculture/viticulture, and medical/societal data will benefit from these new ways of distilling data into knowledge and productive action.
- Curated by:** exa4mind-heurope
- Curation policy:** Only material related to EXA4MIND.
- Created:** November 29, 2022
- Harvesting API:** OAI-PMH Interface

Figure 24 EXA4MIND's Zenodo Repository

Source Code Repository

Advocating for replicability and openness, EXA4MIND will make software with setup scripts for the Extreme Data Database (EDD), the Database Management System (DBMS), FAIR Data Interfaces and the Data Ingest Interfaces and preprocessors (see **Section 5.1.1**) fully available for other developers. The project's own **GitLab**⁴² repository is already live for this purpose (see **Figure 25**).

⁴² GitLab repository website. <https://about.gitlab.com> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

GitLab

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind>

Figure 25 EXA4MIND's Source Code Repository at GitLab

Surveys and Consultations

Following the stakeholder mapping and segmentation, EXA4MIND will shift its focus to tailoring key messages for its main audiences. Online surveys and consultations (e.g., via GDPR-compliant survey management platforms, like the European Commission's very own **EU Survey**⁴³) are extremely powerful tools to establish bi-directional feedback and information flows and reach the project's initial conversion goals in terms of promotion and potential collaboration opportunities (e.g., matchmaking, publishing, joint events).

⁴³ EU Survey website. <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

4.2.2 Peer-reviewed Publications

EXA4MIND aims to publish and contribute to peer-reviewed publications in top refereed scientific journals and conferences, capitalising on the experience from research partners. As a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), one of the primary goals is to ensure the project’s technical achievements and experimental findings are shared and exploited by the larger scientific community working in Extreme Data mining and analytics. **Table 5** shows some of the journals that EXA4MIND has considered for future publication. This list will be reviewed quarterly to include any other suggestions for open access journals where partners could publish their findings and research results.

Journals
IEEE Access
KAIS – Knowledge and Information Systems
The VLDB Journal
IPM – Information Processing and Management
EJIS – European Journal of Information Systems
DMKD – Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery
TKDD – ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data
TKDE – Transactions on Data Engineering
JCIM – Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling
JCTC – Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation
JBC – Journal on Big Data
Big Data
BDCC – Big Data and Cognitive Computing
Big Data and Society
IEEE Transactions on Big Data
IJCV - International Journal on Computer Vision
IEEE TPAMI - IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence

Table 5 Tentative List of Journals Considered for Future Publication

4.2.3 Awareness Publications

Press Releases

EXA4MIND will produce and distribute press releases to mainstream and specialist media outlets to broadcast and highlight the project’s key milestones. Press releases are first shared internally with project partners so they can use them as reference to communicate about the project through their own networks, channels and newsrooms.

The first press release for the project’s launch (see **Figure 26**) was published back in January 2023 and is accessible through Zenodo⁴⁴.

Figure 26 EXA4MIND – First Press Release

Articles and Blog Posts

Publishing online articles, blog posts (see **Figure 27**) and other content pieces on the project’s website and well-known platforms and communication outlets (e.g., **Cordis Wire**⁴⁵, **Horizon Magazine**⁴⁶, **Cordis Research*EU Magazine**⁴⁷, **Digital Innovation Magazine**⁴⁸, **Industry Europe**⁴⁹) and on national/local portals will help maximise the project’s online visibility and reach.

⁴⁴ EXA4MIND First joint press release. <https://zenodo.org/record/7530389> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

⁴⁵ Cordis Wire portal.

https://cordis.europa.eu/login/en?extUrl=https:%2F%2Fcordis.europa.eu%2Fwire%2Fworkspace_en (Accessed 29 June 2023)

⁴⁶ Horizon Magazine website. <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

⁴⁷ Coris Research*eu Magazine website. <https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

⁴⁸ Digital Innovation Magazine. <https://digitalinnovationeu.com> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

⁴⁹ Industry Europe Website. <https://industryeurope.com> (Accessed 29 June 2023)

EXA4MIND

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Latest news, stories, activities and upcoming events

Discover Exa4Mind, with its latest news, stories, activities and upcoming events.

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Why is EXA4MIND important and who is behind the project?

Read More

Jan Martinovic
EXA4MIND Project coordinator welcomes you on board

EXA4MIND project coordinator, Jan Martinovic, welcomes you on board

Read More

Figure 27 EXA4MIND's Website – News Section and Blog Entries

4.2.4 Events

Events (e.g., conferences, congresses, seminars, trade fairs, exhibitions) are a strategic mechanism to put EXA4MIND's results under the spotlight, while actively interacting and engaging with multiple stakeholders. **Table 6** presents the list of events that the consortium has:

- ◆ Already attended on behalf of EXA4MIND as part of the project's networking and outreach strategy.

- ♦ Identified as potential upcoming opportunities to participate and share EXA4MIND’s insights and progress.

Event	Start Date	Location	Status
<u>ISGC – International Symposium on Grids and Clouds 2023</u> (With the Environmental Computing Workshop)	19-24/03/2023	Taipei, TW	Presented
<u>EuroHPC Summit 2023</u>	20-23/03/2023	Gothenburg, SE	Presented
<u>ITS European Congress</u>	22-24/05/2023	Lisbon, PT	Presented
<u>ISC High Performance 2023</u>	21-25/05/2023	Hamburg, DE	Presented
<u>Data Week 23</u>	13-15/06/2023	Lulea, SE	Panellist
<u>CVPR – The IEEE / CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference</u>	18-22/06/2023	Vancouver, CA	Attended
<u>EUDAT Summer School</u>	26-30/06/2023	Kajaani, Finland	Presented
<u>Ostrava EDIH Day</u>	10-05-2023	Ostrava, CR	Attended
<u>EuChems CompChem 2023</u>	27-31/08/2023	Thessaloniki, GR	Upcoming
<u>International Conference on Very Large Databases</u>	28-08/01-09/2023	Vancouver, CA	Upcoming
<u>TeraTech 2023</u>	04-08/09/2023	Aizu-Wakamatsu, JP	Upcoming
<u>AI & Big Data Expo Europe</u>	26-27/09/2023	Amsterdam, NL	Upcoming
<u>ICCV – International Conference on Computer Vision</u>	02-06/10/2023	Paris, FR	Upcoming
<u>EU Industry Days</u>	04-06/10/2023	Málaga, ES	Upcoming
<u>CIKM – ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management</u>	21-25/10/2023	Birmingham, UK	Upcoming
<u>International Data Week 2023</u> (with RDA Plenary 21)	23-26/10/2023	Salzburg, AT	Upcoming
<u>FIC – International Cybersecurity Forum</u>	25-26/10/2023	Montreal, CA	Upcoming
<u>EBDVF – European Big Data Value Forum</u>	25-27/10/2023	Valencia, ES	Upcoming
<u>The International Conference for High-Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis (SC23)</u>	12-17/11/2023	Denver, US	Upcoming
<u>SaaS Monster</u>	13-16/11/2023	Lisbon, PT	Upcoming
<u>Big Data Europe 2023</u>	21-24/11/2023	Vilnius, LT	Upcoming
<u>AI & Big Data Expo Global</u>	30/11-01/12/2023	London, UK	Upcoming
<u>ICDM – International Conference on Data Mining</u>	01-04/12/2023	Shanghai, CH	Upcoming

<u>SIGIR – International Conference on Research on Development in Information Retrieval</u>	10-14/03/2024	Sheffield, UK	Upcoming
<u>FIC - International Cybersecurity Forum</u>	26-28/03/2024	Lille, FR	Upcoming
<u>Open Data Science conference 2024</u>	TBC	TBC	Upcoming
<u>CDO Europe Exchange</u>	TBC	TBC	Upcoming

Table 6 List of Relevant Past and Upcoming Events for EXA4MIND

5 Exploitation plan

With the aim to reach TRL5, EXA4MIND will provide a platform and its components as frameworks and developer tool kits adapted to further developments up to TRL8 and 9. Therefore, the exploitation plan will focus on alerting, informing and enabling communities in research/public sectors and private sectors about the opportunities to build upon EXA4MIND developments and application cases to then reach a TRL8 stage of development, with a commercial/non-commercial perspective.

In addition, EXA4MIND will facilitate further developments by packaging the platform and its sub-components (code, software, services, documentation and training) and making them accessible in an open-source approach.

In relationship with the communication and dissemination plans, as seen above, the exploitation plan will include structured promotional efforts to promote and attract developers and their communities both in public/research sectors and the private sector.

EXA4MIND's exploitation plan will be structured around the following actions:

- ◆ **Guidelines** on market evolutions and trends for Extreme Data analytics.
- ◆ A **Strategic Research and Innovation agenda** to align with Digital Sovereignty policies and regulations in the EU.
- ◆ **Packaging** of EXA4MIND **outputs** for further exploitation (post TRL5) and definition of a roadmap toward pre-commercialization (TRL8/9).
- ◆ **Services, training** and **documentation** to support developers.
- ◆ Promotion of the EXA4MIND **platform** and **components** in public and private developer communities and wider end-user communities.
- ◆ **Partnering** with industry relays (key industry players, industry & regulatory bodies – i.e., GAIA-X, EuroHPC, BDVA, EUDAT), existing HPC/HPDA/AI/cloud platforms, EU-funded projects H2020 and Horizon Europe, as identified in the Engagement Strategy.

These points will be further addressed in D7.3 (EXA4MIND 2024b) and D7.5 (EXA4MIND 2025b), both exclusively dedicated to the market analysis and exploitation review. Exploitation activity is planned to start on month 9 and the first Market Analysis and Exploitation Report will be presented in month 18. This first part will be dedicated to collect all market information, technology and regulatory ecosystems relevant to the project. This will be monitored to support the building of efficient exploitation plans and measures, involving the EXAKI (EXA4MIND Kickstarter Initiative) service platform. From month 24, the EXAKI kick-starter initiative will be launched to foster adoption of the EXA4MIND platforms and its KEAs. The Final Market Analysis and Exploitation Report will be submitted in month 36.

5.1 Key Exploitation Assets (KEAs)

EXA4MIND plans to achieve the development of multiple Key Exploitable Assets (KEAs) and these are classified into two categories:

- ♦ **Tools and Technologies:** the building blocks for Extreme Data analytics.
- ♦ **Application Cases:** the mechanisms to test Extreme Data analytics.

The KEAs below are the foundation of the exploitation plan and market positioning, to be further defined by D7.3 (EXA4MIND 2024b) in month 18.

5.1.1 Tools and Technologies – Building blocks KEAs

KEA #1 – EXA4MIND Extreme Data Database Platform (EDD)

EDD will be a software stack composed of assets provided by KEA #2, KEA #3 and KEA #4 (DBMS instances, object storages, data preprocessing pipeline and AQIS querying system) tied together by unified and automated deployment on target infrastructure, thus enabling the EDD portability.

KEA #2 - EXA4MIND DBMS-to-Supercomputing Bridge

The bridge will be an API designed to trigger staging/caching/access mechanisms in order to make DBMS extreme data available for supercomputing (HPC/cloud) and get results back together with back-end asynchronous staging/caching mechanisms.

KEA #3 – EXA4MIND DBMS FAIR Data Interfaces

These interfaces will be an API/back-end to equip data in DBMS with persistent identifiers and metadata, and to make them FAIR. This will provide open access to DBMS Extreme Data within the frameworks of EOSC and European Data Spaces.

KEA #4 – EXA4MIND Mining Toolbox (AQIS)

The AQIS will allow for optimised database queries on the EDD, across different DBMS and generally data-system back-ends. It will simplify/unify queries, and it will accelerate them with appropriate indexing strategies.

5.1.2 Application Cases KEAs

KEA #5 – IT4I@VSB Scientific Application Case Extension by EXA4MIND Platform

An innovative automated data mining system for systematic improvement of molecular simulations accuracy and predictability (ADAMS4SIMS) brings recent Big Data and enabling AI into the force fields (FF) testing and development, driving a change in FF development paradigms. Automated AI/ML workflows will allow for more robust molecular dynamics (MD) modelling in (bio)chemical research, drug design and (bio/nano) molecular design as a whole.

KEA #6 – VALEO Industry Application Case Extension by EXA4MIND Platform

This application case will develop tools which will be integrated into VALEO annotation process. These tools will be able to manage very high quantities of metadata and will also accelerate the development of VALEO's innovation research and application. Additional to automatic annotation extraction, we will leverage the newly appearing foundational image/language models allowing for smart data querying and open vocabulary rare object discovery.

KEA #7 – TERRAVIEW SME Application Case Extension by EXA4MIND Platform

TERRAVIEW will develop a tightly integrated subsystem of TerraviewOS that will enable optimised data ingestion and distribution of all data (satellite, IoT, documents) related to the management of vineyards. This subsystem will also support the execution of TerraviewOS specific computations in order to provide information and actionable insights to TERRAVIEW's customers. The data ingested, the data calculated and metadata will also be made available.

KEA #8 – ALTRNATIV SME Application Case Extension by EXA4MIND Platform

This application case will enable accessible treatment of massive & Extreme Data by creating an ergonomic interface for SME end-users exploiting the EDD infrastructure. This interface will allow the users to get precise insights into health/society patterns by combining and normalising complex data sources.

KEA #9 – Data Ingest Interfaces and Preprocessors

These data ingest interfaces & preprocessors will be flexible adaptors to ingest data into the EDD with push- and pull-based interfaces, in particular REST APIs. Modularised, flexibly configured preprocessing tools will be fed by the ingest adaptors and will harmonise data for all application cases.

5.1.3 The EXAKI Platform

As an integral part of EXA4MIND exploitation plans, the consortium will develop the EXAKI (EXA4MIND Kickstarter Initiative) service platform to maximise the impact towards application projects holders, developer communities, researchers, other EU funded research projects, large industries, SMEs and start-ups.

The EXAKI platform will be open to partnerships with other significant technology partners in Europe to maximise its efficiency and impact. Starting from month 24, EXA4MIND will set up EXAKI to accompany any project of application development intending to use the EXA4MIND Platform or its Key Exploitable Assets (KEAs) to help and kickstart successful exploitation by project holders.

The initiative will liaise with DIHs across Europe for service integration with their already existing portfolios (e.g., Test before invest, Skills and training, Support to find investments, Innovation ecosystem and Networking), focusing on the following services:

- ◆ Application project assessment,
- ◆ Application design coaching,
- ◆ Application technical development coaching,
- ◆ Training,
- ◆ Technical advice and support to developers,
- ◆ Networking assistance.

The initial EXAKI detailed plan will be presented in D7.3 (**EXA4MIND 2024b**) in month 18 and a more detailed presentation of the outcomes will be presented in D7.5 (**EXA4MIND 2025b**) in month 36.

5.1.4 IPR Management

EXA4MIND will consider **three main elements** of an effective system to protect and exploit Intellectual Property (IP):

- ◆ A system that enables the **protection of IP** (e.g., patents, copyrights, brand, industrial design) that includes clarity about the ownership and use of IP rights (IPR), the rights and freedom of parties to transfer (assign) IP, and the freedom to publish.
- ◆ A **technology transfer framework**, preferably with the support of specialised knowledge transfer offices with professional staff, such as the European IPR Helpdesk.
- ◆ A **fair law enforcement** system in each partner's country caters to dispute settlements and award penalties and sanctions where appropriate. Specific IPR issues will be identified and addressed as per the Consortium Agreement.

The basic principle is that foreground knowledge, i.e., created within (or resulting from) the project, belongs to the project partner who generated it. If knowledge is developed jointly and separate parts cannot be distinguished, it will be jointly owned unless the contractors concerned agree on a different solution.

6 Standardisation and Open Source

From month 13 onwards, EXA4MIND will set out a roadmap for contributing to different standardisation technical committees and open-source communities (see **Table 7**). This activity will:

- ◆ Identify applicable existing standards meaningful for the operation of the work plan, considering ongoing developments by related technical committees in the field.
- ◆ Implement a strategy to engage these bodies, considering which are the most relevant and to what extent the relationship should be established.
- ◆ Facilitate and promote the inclusion of the outcomes in future new or revised standards, feeding the selected SDOs and committees with proposals ready for discussion and inclusion in the future development of new standards or revised ones.

Body	Scope
<u>EUDAT</u>	EXA4MIND will benefit from strong cooperation with EUDAT, one of the largest infrastructures of integrated data services and resources for research in Europe, with a network of 20+ EU research organisations, data and computing centres. Aiming at extending EUDAT approaches to the DBMS Extreme Data world, we will use EUDAT open-source technology and feedback results to the EUDAT ecosystem.
<u>RDA</u>	The Research Data Alliance (RDA) is ‘the’ international body for issuing recommendations in Research Data Management, which are often the basis for EU standards. BADW-LRZ takes part in RDA subgroups (e.g., RD Architectures in Research Institutions IG – RDARI), and thus can bring in experience from EXA4MIND into RDA. On the other hand, we make sure EXA4MIND follows relevant recommendations.
<u>ISO23150</u>	Road vehicles – data communication between sensors and data fusion unit for automated driving functions – logical interface.
<u>CLEPA</u>	Euro NCAP active safety.
<u>ASAM Open SCENARIO</u>	The standard defines a file format for the description of the dynamic content of driving and traffic simulators. The primary use-case of Open SCENARIO is to describe complex, synchronised manoeuvres that involve multiple entities like vehicles, pedestrians and other traffic participants.
<u>StandICT.eu</u>	The European ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility empowers EU ICT standardisation experts in top-notch intentional SDOs and technical committees, with 700+ members.

Table 7 Relevant Standardisation Technical Committees for EXA4MIND

7 Internal Governance and Monitoring

Internal governance and a continuous monitoring of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plans are fundamental to EXA4MIND's success. They empower the consortium to anticipate and mitigate any deviations affecting the project's timeline or its resource allocation. It also addresses potential implementation issues and helps assess whether further action is required to ensure targets are met.

This section explores what procedures have already been put in place for EXA4MIND specifically, and how they fit into the project's overall operation.

7.1 Internal Governance and Communication Guidelines

A solid internal governance plan is key to ensure that interests are aligned within the consortium, and that everybody is duly informed of the latest developments. With this goal in mind, WP7-specific internal follow-up meetings have been scheduled on a monthly basis, and internal communication guidelines (see [Figure 28](#)) have been produced to make sure all partners communicate about EXA4MIND following both brand identity guidelines and observing the mandatory provisions set by the European Commission (e.g., correctly displaying the official disclaimers about visibility and transparency of public funding).

Some of EXA4MIND's ongoing internal governance mechanisms are as follows:

- ◆ **WP7 team:** all consortium partners have appointed representatives to attend WP7 follow-up meetings and contribute to the smooth execution of all agreed upon communication and dissemination activities.
- ◆ **Prior notice of any planned publication:** all consortium partners have appointed a member to the group which will be asked before publishing any output outside the consortium to confirm that the information can be published. Member of this group is a responsible person that will be asked before publishing any output outside the consortium to confirm that the information to be published can be public.
- ◆ **EXA4MIND's glossary:** a project glossary is in the works to create a compilation of key terms and ideas that will contribute to better alignment communication-wise and improved understanding of the project's unified vision among the consortium.
- ◆ **Internal checkpoints:** quarterly internal reports are produced and presented to inform consortium members about up-and-coming campaigns and overall outreach highlights. Additionally, when relevant, we liaise directly with communication departments to further leverage C&D capabilities within the project.
- ◆ **Quality assurance:** project results and formal deliverables will undergo a quality control process of internal project verification and document reviews prior to their timely submission to the European Commission. At least 2-3 internal reviewers will be assigned to review documents prior to the approval by the coordinator team and

submission to the European Commission. Quality manager ensures that the project outputs (reports, documentation, software, etc.) have the expected excellent quality by the appropriate review mechanisms which were set up at the beginning of the project.

Figure 28 EXA4MIND's Internal Communication Guidelines Extract

7.2 Continuous monitoring

Internal C&D reporting tools and resources (see **Figure 29**) have already been made available to all partners in the project, so that they are able to track their individual communication and dissemination efforts. These tools will become the backbone supporting the official reporting and follow-up on communication, dissemination and exploitation related efforts (e.g., status on EXA4MIND's publication pipelines, event agenda, periodic updates on KPIs).

The details on how these tools have been set up and are currently being operated are provided below.

Figure 29 EXA4MIND – Internal Monitoring Tools

7.2.1 C&D Database

This internal database is a compilation of shared resources available from each partner for outreach purposes (e.g., relevant networks, newsletters and magazines, journal access). This database will be periodically updated to pool new resources and serve as a common knowledge base for all outreach efforts.

7.2.2 Outreach Tracker

This tracker lists and reports efforts linked to communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project and its results. Whenever a partner dedicates efforts/resources to contribute to and drive forward the project’s outreach strategy, the tracker collates their actions to keep full traceability and collect relevant evidence towards the official reporting to the European Commission.

7.2.3 Editorial Calendar

EXA4MIND C&D plan establishes quarterly communication cycles that include a set of specific actions (e.g., ad hoc campaigns in social media). Action in a given cycle are reviewed on a weekly basis to ensure its appropriateness within the project’s wider context. These cycles are managed via the project’s editorial calendar, conceived to plan out and schedule posts and news pieces, identify upcoming opportunities and maintain a regular stream of content through our social media channels. This tool also helps keep track of all external mentions, articles or press features for the project.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable outlines EXA4MIND stakeholder collaboration framework and communication and dissemination strategies, as well as the project approach towards exploitation of results for business, standardisation and IPR purposes. All these tasks fall into the scope of WP7 – Outreach, Exploitation and Collaboration.

This document shows the work done in the first 6 months of the project and also serves as a preliminary snapshot for EXA4MIND communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Due to its release in the early stages of the project and the ever-changing nature of innovation, these strategies might be subject to changes throughout the project’s lifespan. Therefore, this can be considered a living document and any and all changes will be adequately reflected in successive iterations of upcoming deliverables.

With regards to the stakeholder collaboration framework, EXA4MIND has already started to identify and evaluate synergies across a wide spectrum of entities, with the aim of understanding the ecosystem of actors who might be interested in the project findings, and to develop a specific value proposition and C&D strategy for each category.

For what concerns communication and dissemination, several major milestones have already been accomplished: EXA4MIND’s visual identity and key branding assets have been produced, main digital channels for the project have been set up and consolidated, and several joint efforts on the publication and promotional fronts have successfully come into fruition.

In the short term, EXA4MIND will take its first steps in mapping out an exploitation roadmap. For that purpose, this deliverable introduces the preliminary list of project’s KEAs and an initial overview of the EXAKI platform, a service platform that the consortium will develop to focus on services such as design and technical development coaching, training, technical advice, support to developers and networking assistance. The same is true for the project’s envisioned contributions to standardisation and open source initiatives, for which an initial approach is also provided.

9 References

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- EXA4MIND (2024a). Deliverable D7.2 Dissemination & Communication Interim Report.
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